

STRATEGY COMPARISON FOR SEMANTIC ZERO-SHOT TAXONOMY FILTERS

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Abstract

This contribution extends and tests ideas from sentence-transformer-based zero-shot text classification to the problem of building a taxonomy filter which can be used for assigning large quantities of documents to user-defined thematic groups.

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Motivation

In information retrieval, categorised filtering is a way of supporting users in formulating their information needs in an efficient way: Instead of having to provide an explicit specification of the search request, the user can select from an existing list of available categories or tags.

Many collections of documents provided by publishers, libraries, or archives are structured in terms of subject-specific categories that can be used within their domains. Traditionally, assigning documents to categories is an effortful manual process. Progress in machine learning classification algorithms has made it possible to automatize this task in a generally acceptable manner, provided a sufficient number of labelled example documents from all categories is put into the training process.

The latter requirement, however, is a serious obstacle for a flexible use over a broad range of domains and in areas with limited amount of training data available.

It is therefore attractive to explore how the recently proposed method of transformer-based zero-shot text classification [1] can be applied to building taxonomy filters.

Objective

The aim of this contribution is to suggest and compare methods with the following characteristics, which will be explicated below:

1. The method should work with any user-provided commented taxonomic category system.
2. The method should not require taxonomy-specific training.
3. Time-consuming pre-processing steps for each document should not depend on the individual taxonomy categories.

A taxonomy for documents is a hierarchical tree-like system of categories (groups of documents) which covers a domain of interest. Taxonomies are abundant in scientific, economic, and normative classification schemes. Formalised, they are part of the W3C-recommended Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS). A commented taxonomy adds a short description to each taxonomy label.

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If users want to set up specialised taxonomies for their purposes, it is much easier to provide a short description than to collect a sufficiently large set of labelled examples. General purpose language models which are able to detect semantic similarity can then be used to match documents to taxonomic descriptions.

However, if this matching for N documents and M categories requires the encoding of NM text sequence pairs it becomes inefficient. For large scale applications it is therefore important to employ the bi-encoder strategy of sentence transformers [2] which needs just $N+M$ encodings – individually on documents and on category descriptions.

Method

A simple baseline implementation of a taxonomy filter obeying the first two objectives can be easily realised by directly using the *zero-shot classification pipeline* of *Hugging Face* [3]. The third objective can be achieved by confining to its *sentence similarity pipeline*.

This contribution reports on ongoing work regarding the refinement of taxonomy filters through category assignments which go beyond a gross similarity score by

- a) Breaking down the documents into single sentences and computing a weighted aggregated category vote,
- b) Taking into account hierarchical consistency as a criterion for category assignment.

Various variants of such taxonomy filters will be tested and compared on the basis of datasets and taxonomies from different domains.

These examples also show the degree to which approximate nearest neighbourhood computations in the underlying embedding space can replace exact calculations as a further performance improvement for large scale applications.

REFERENCES

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- [3] <https://github.com/huggingface/transformers>